

TEACHING VOCABULARY AT DIFFERENT LEVELS

Sotvoldiyeva Mohidil¹, Ismonqulova Nigora²

¹Guliston davlat universiteti 4- bosqich talabasi

²Guliston davlat universiteti Filologiya fakulteti Xorijiy til fani o'qtuvchisi
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Annontatsion: This part refers to the learning of vocabulary in English, and the word Lexis is also used.

Key words: comprehension, frequently, already, Intermediate level

For a better comprehension of this work, we will define the terms Vocabulary , Lexis and Lexicon. Vocabulary and Lexis refer to all the words in a particular language , and in the dictionary we can find the same definition for both of them; According to the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English , vocabulary and lexis refer to all the words in a particular language . However , Vocabulary is used most commonly when we want to refer to the words used in particular context or known to a particular person . On the other side , we also have the term Lexicon, which different from the two previous words , refers to all the words and phrases used in a language or that a particular person knows; this means that not only words are considered but also the knowledge and comprehension of the person who uses it. Therefore vocabulary is words.

Types of vocabulary Active vocabulary

This type of vocabulary makes reference to the ones student have learnt and that are expected to be used, that is , to be put into practice . Thus with the students at basic level, it will be an excellent idea to provide them of vocabulary that they will use however, with the upper level students the acquisition of basic vocabulary will not be very notorious , that is expressed by Harmer who states that with the students of the intermediate and advanced level, this will be more difficult since they have already acquired more vocabulary and therefore , it will be hard to distinguish which words are active and which ones are passive, sometimes they believe they are not making much progress nor ate learning fast.

Passive vocabulary With this vocabulary , students will just have to understand ; there will not be need to use frequently. For example when students read a text or piece of writing , they do not learn all the words , but the main ones. However, there can also be some passive words that suddenly become active if the situation or context provokes their use. On the other hand, if a person does

not have a stored word in his/her passive vocabulary, it will be difficult that words become part of his/ her active vocabulary.

Basic level At basic level the students can learn and get familiarized just with words they will use and that are around them. Many times books contain complex words that make it difficult for student to learn. It is important that the teacher is aware that learning a foreign language is difficult and that students are beginning to get familiarized with English. So it is probable that each word they encounter catches their attention just if it is part of an experience for them.

Intermediate level Teachers very often teach the same vocabulary to students at intermediate level and basic, and this is because lessons include many words that form part of students' daily life. However, this vocabulary is used more often than before since teachers tend to speak in English most time of the lesson and this lets students acquire more vocabulary with just listening to their teachers.

Advanced level

Students at advanced level communicative as they have already learnt basic structures of the target languages and have acquired a wide range of vocabulary. In spite of the fact that students have already acquired a great amount of words, it is necessary that the teacher pays attention to the use students make of words, that is, the teacher must now focus if students use the words adequately in spoken and writing task. At this level students become independent and responsible for their learning, if they want to know the meaning of an unknown word, they can use their dictionary.

Using games in teaching vocabulary skills develops habits and skills of dialogue speech, promotes students' speaking initiatives and enhances the natural communicative orientation of the lesson. The authors suppose that while playing games students involuntarily memorize new lexical and grammar material. Thus using games in foreign language teaching is one of the most effective ways that provide students with speaking opportunities and at the same time, motivate them.

References:

1. "foreign language" 2019

2. "This part refers to 2012"

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